

#6: Mitigating the risks of tipping points

To reduce the risks associated with climate tipping points, it is essential to synthesise knowledge on their likelihood, timing, and potential impacts. TipESM will develop a unique **Tipping Point Risk Register**, aligned with the IPCC approach to risk assessment. The Risk Register will include information on tipping element thresholds, timescales, and impacts at both global and regional levels, such as habitat loss, economic disruption, and human health risks.

Action

TipESM will constrain future tipping point risks by reducing uncertainties in Earth System Models and refining the overall assessment of the likelihood of tipping events. This will be achieved through a combination of observation-based constraints, advanced modelling techniques, and artificial intelligence including the use of emergent constraint methods to improve probability and impact estimates. This will be combined with an assessment of exposure and vulnerability to impacts, considering the interaction between tipping in natural and human systems and their sensitivity to crossing key thresholds, such as changes in extreme weather events. TipESM will also develop safe emission pathways to avoid crossing tipping points and associated extreme event thresholds. These pathways will be dynamic and responsive, adapting continuously to updated climate observations and the proximity of the Earth system to critical tipping points.

By synthesising knowledge on the likelihood and impacts of crossing tipping points, TipESM will:

- Reduce uncertainty in model projections of key climate variables associated with tipping events
- Provide a unique tipping point risk register
- Develop safe emission pathways to avoid crossing tipping points and extreme event thresholds
- Provide a best estimate of the pathway and remaining carbon budget to minimise the risk of crossing certain tipping point thresholds, including extreme and compound event thresholds

The project

TipESM brings together scientists from a range of disciplines to deliver a step change in our understanding of climate tipping points in the Earth system, including their impact on ecosystems and society, combined with a set of early warning indicators and safe future emission pathways that minimise the risk of exceeding such tipping points.

Project partners and associated partners

- Danish Meteorological Institute
- Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
- The French National Centre for Scientific Research (and their affiliated entities)
- The Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute
- University of Bergen
- The Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research
- Barcelona Institute for Global Health
- University of Leeds
- Met Office UK
- University of Reading
- University of Liverpool
- University of Bern
- Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research

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Constraining future tipping point risks and providing safe mitigation emission pathways

TipESM will reduce uncertainty in the estimated likelihood of tipping point crossing by constraining models and impact projections using observation-based constraints on key physical and biogeochemical processes, in combination with artificial intelligence (AI) and emergent constraint methods. We aim to improve these empirical methods by applying several predictors for a given variable related to a tipping element and by using AI approaches for regression.

TipESM will develop safe emission pathways, including multiple targets beyond global warming, to avoid crossing tipping points and extreme event thresholds. TipESM will develop adaptive emissions scenarios in which emissions are iteratively adjusted, allowing for dynamic adjustments based on realised changes and the proximity to tipping points. We will provide our best estimate of the pathway and remaining carbon budget to minimise the chance of crossing certain Earth system tipping thresholds, including extreme and compound event thresholds.

By synthesising knowledge on the likelihood and impacts of crossing tipping points, TipESM will:

- Reduce uncertainty in model projections of key climate variables associated with tipping events
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TipESM - Exploring Tipping Points and Their Impacts Using Earth System Models

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Expected impacts of TipESM

The key objectives of the project are to:

- Advance knowledge and solutions in Earth system science, pathways to climate neutrality, climate change adaptation, climate services, social science for climate action and understanding of climate-ecosystem interactions
- Contribute substantially to key international assessments (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, and the European Environment Agency)
- Increase the transparency, robustness, trustworthiness and practical usability of the knowledge base on climate and Earth system change for use by policymakers, practitioners, other stakeholders and citizens
- Strengthen the European Research Area with increased knowledge of the risks of crossing climate tipping points

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